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TRACING THE EVOLUTION OF THE CONCEPT OF CITIZENSHIP

WITH RESPECT TO CITIZENSHIP AMENDMENT ACT 2019

Author

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ABSTRACT

The paper first analyses the concept of citizenship throughout history, illustrating how the concept of citizenship has varied and changed throughout the years and has constantly been exclusionary, depending heavily on an 'other' to define itself coherently. With this perspective, the paper then looks at the controversial Citizenship Amendment Act of 2019, particularly the arguments surrounding it. After a critical review of the arguments, it takes up the view that the whole affair was concocted as a vote banking strategy for the majoritarian party. The various citizenship laws of other countries have been analysed in terms of their leniency towards granting citizenship. Furthermore, the economic question of migrants is briefly discussed, with data showing the increase of remittances by migrants from nine different countries. The paper concludes by questioning whether a concept of 'citizen' is actually meaningful, given our current humanitarian issues and argues for replacing the concept of 'citizen' with that of a 'cosmopolitan.'

1. INTRODUCTION

The Citizenship Amendment Act was passed during a year of massive upheaval. Thousands of people, usually unconcerned with politics, were transformed into political activists and took to the streets to express their vehement dissatisfaction. Thousands more became political activists in response to the dissatisfied and launched protests in support of the Act. This led to a barrage of communal violence across states, in which many lost their lives and livelihoods.

Yet curiously enough, discussion on the Act itself, most notably on its feasibility and its potential impact, have been strangely absent. Even much more fundamentally, what exactly is the Act itself and why should we bother passing it has also received scant attention. The debates, of which have been many on television, have mostly been in the traditional quagmire of the left vs right. The television right claiming that the Act is necessary for the future of benefit "persecuted minorities", while the television left denouncing the Act for a variety of reasons such as "Against the constitution" and "Against secularism".

This paper goes further back in search of answers. The paper tries to go back all the way to the Ancient Greeks to find out what exactly did "Citizenship" mean to them and did they think it was so big an issue as to fight tooth and nail over it as our fellow Indians have done. No doubt, the concept of "Citizen" has evolved from the Greek times and constitutes something more than what it was for them. Although the concept itself has evolved since the Greeks, it hasn't evolved much from the time of the French Revolution. Notably, most of the things legal and such have been fairly unmodified since the days of their rebirth in the French Revolution. The Indian Constitution has based itself squarely on the French Republican values of "Liberty, Equality and Fraternity". The genesis (or re-genesis) of the concept of citizenship in the French Revolution is somewhat surprising, as it turns out that the main purpose of the new citizenship was to exclusively gain the right (to the state) to boot supposed foreigners.

And to boot foreigners was exactly what the conservatives at the Indian Parliament, discussing the laws related to citizenship, precisely had in mind. The paper points out the debates on the with the conservatives were very concerned about losing their 'national identity by making citizenship 'cheap'. It is left for the reader to wonder how exactly is one supposed to make citizenship 'expensive' and why should anyone go about doing so. Although the Parliament conservatives did not explicitly say so, one can easily discern that what they wanted was citizenship based on religion, particularly the Hindu and Sikh religions. They reasoned that since Pakistan was an exclusively 'Muslim state', they must have a corresponding 'Hindu state' to even the power of the Hindu people.

With this perspective, it becomes clear that the whole debate on the Act was in part a continuation of a communal debate that happened long before. The implicit philosophical question was, "What religion should an Indian citizen have?" The answer to the given question was the difference between the left and the right. Does this mean that the right-wing ruling party had this in mind when it advocated for and then subsequently implemented this Act, in other words, to fulfil the vision of the Constituent Assembly conservatives?

The answer, when looked at the facts, is a very likely 'no'. We often forget that political parties are akin to business organizations, that is, they say things that are likely to woo their clientele and do what benefits the party, even at the expense of the clientele. At least in these days, a political party is mostly concerned with maximizing votes, just like a business organization is concerned with maximizing profits. The same is the case with the ruling right-wing party. They pulled the Act through because they anticipated that it would lead them to more votes. Whether or not they have succeeded is difficult to tell.

The paper then takes a detour into other countries and see how they have particularly dealt with citizenships and immigrants, in contrast to the Indian reaction. Given the right-wing obsession with the immigrants supposedly 'stealing our jobs', it is seen that the most developed countries have the most lenient citizenship requirements and often very high rates of migration. These policies have, almost in all cases, directly contributed to the development of the countries. Furthermore, for the past twenty years, remittances sent home by migrants have consistently increased, this is shown by a sample of nine countries from all over the world.

Given the rather pessimistic predicament we find ourselves in, with time-honoured concepts such as 'citizenship', a once source of pride, being found out as nothing more than a ploy to kick out foreigners, where do we go from here? The answer is rather difficult, and therefore simple answers are simply not possible. In sketching a possible answer, it seems fruitful to go back to the Greeks. The feasibility of the Greek position is upto the population as a whole to decide.

2. HISTORICAL EVOLUTION

2.1 Citizenship in Antiquity

The Oxford Dictionary defines a citizen as "a person who has the legal right to belong to a particular country". Although appropriate for our times, it simply does not do justice to the diverse history of the term itself. The term originated in the Greek polis, the word "Polis" roughly translated to something that is closed; in this context, it referred to a citadel.

All free men, barring women and slaves, living in this polis were its 'citizens'. This meant that they had a role in governing its affairs. One can easily see how profoundly democratic (allowing all 'Citizens' to govern the affairs of the community) and undemocratic (excluding women and slaves) these citadels were.

The Greek citizens, however, didn't really care much for other people. Even if they conquered some foreigners, they didn't extend the unfortunates a chance in 'governing the affairs of the government'.

It was with this perspective that Aristotle defined citizens as "a person (freeman) who will have a direct and active role in the administration of the state". Keeping in mind that only slaves and women were not allowed to participate in all the ruling directly, one may wonder what Aristotle would think about our current society.

Next, the Romans conquered the Greeks and decided, unlike the Greeks, to actually give non-Romans a chance to be a Roman. That is, they gave away 'citizenships'. However, they also reduced some of the perks that being a citizen gave. No longer could a citizen directly participate in the ruling. They only could demand to be tried in court if they were accused of a crime.

The right to trial in a proper court was also rather limited. The famous Paul the Apostle, when being persecuted by a local mob, yelled, "I am a Roman Citizen". The mob heard him, recognized his rights, and took him to a proper Roman court. The trial concluded with the court imprisoning him for six years and then finally beheading him. So much for being a "Roman Citizen".

Actually, if Paul weren't a Roman, they would have probably done the same thing to him as they did to a person whom Paul greatly admired; Jesus Christ. Would Paul have preferred to be crucified? We will never know.

Another different aspect of Roman citizenship was that it had ranks. Different people qualified for different ranks of citizenship, and these ranks also dictated what powers the citizens had. For example, after conquering the surrounding Latin region and subjugating its population, the Romans offered Latin citizenships. These citizenships were literally second-class citizenships as they did not allow the Latins to have the same rights as Romans. When they extended the Empire even further and subjugated the Italians, they gave citizenships to them also, although the citizenships were third-class. There were also the people called 'pregreni'. These were people who lived in Rome but had no rights.

Even then, just as now, there were people who thought that giving these people citizenships, although second and third-class ones, was a very bad idea. "Don't you realize they'll take over everything?" said a Roman opponent of exclusive citizenships. This was in 27 B.C. Who was that who suggested that humans are becoming more tolerant?

2.2 Citizenship in Modern Times

As we have seen, the Oxford definition of citizenship is simply nothing of the kind that was actually practised in antiquity. Aristotle, if he were to hear it, would have found it to be entirely incoherent. The question then is, where did this Oxford definition come from? The answer, it came from the aftermath of the French Revolution, with many additions along the way.

For better or worse, we owe a lot of our current institution to the French Revolution. Our conceptions of Democracy, Human Rights, Legal Codes, and many of our modern ideologies, in one way or the other, can be traced back to the French Revolution. The modern concept of citizenship, the one in which one has a 'legal right to belong to a country', was indeed a product of the French Revolution.

One of the first things done after the revolution was the establishment of what is called "bourgeois society". Before the French Revolution, the French society was highly inegalitarian, with some individuals having a great deal of more legal privileges than others, so much so that speaking of 'common rights' was more or less impossible. The nobility and the clergy were the chief beneficiaries of these privileges; they were exempted from taxes, were entitled to the highest posts in the government and so on. The establishment of 'bourgeois society' revoked all these privileges for the few and transformed them into common law for all. Equality and the legal right to own private property were established and enforced. From this came forth the concept of a Nation-State and, following it, the modern conception of citizenship.

Although the early revolutionaries were explicitly cosmopolitan, calling for France to welcome all people of the Earth, the revolution, later on, took rather xenophobic turns. Why this turn happened is still unclear. Foreign war, civil insurrection and factional struggle did indeed play a major role, but it can plausibly be argued that the seeds of xenophobia were already present in the formation of the Nation-State. This argument is taken up by William Brubaker as he argues, "A nation-state is a nation's state, the state of and for a particular, bounded, sovereign nation, to which foreigners, by definition, do not belong. Legally homogeneous internally, it is by virtue of this very fact more sharply bounded externally than an internally heterogeneous state such as pre-revolutionary France. Sharp external boundedness, to be sure, does not dictate the terms on which resident foreigners are to be treated: but it does mark them clearly and axiomatically as outsiders - indeed as paradigmatic outsiders." (Brubaker, 1989).

The citizenship experience of the French Revolution seems as if the concept of 'citizen', born out of the right to legal equality and right to own private property, acquires its force by contrasting itself with the 'foreigner'. Is this experienced generally? Or is it specific to France due to its own history? If a country transitions to a Nation-State, will it focus a great deal of attention on defining who are its citizens? While we cannot hope to answer all these questions now, we can illustrate another historical example to showcase the point. For this, we have to go back (or forwards if you were still in the French Revolution) to the Parliamentary debates raging in India.

2.3 Citizenship Debates in the Indian Parliament

A year before declaring India a Republic and the year after it, the Constituent Assembly spent a considerable amount debating the chapter on citizenship. Dr Ambedkar was of the opinion that although 'citizenship' should be incorporated in the Constitution, its details should be left out for the Parliament to deliberate on. This view was accepted, and hence there ensued lengthy debates on the question of on what basis should the newly formed Indian government grant citizenship to its residents. The participants of the debate mainly consisted of two groups, the liberals who wanted citizenship based on birth and domicile, and the conservatives who wanted citizenship firmly based on ancestry. Keep in mind that during the time of these debates, the partition of India had recently occurred, causing these debates to be deeply coloured by religious and nationalistic concerns. P.S. Deshmukh, from the conservative side of the debate, argued:

"As I have already pointed out one of the sub-clauses says anybody who has chosen to stay in India for five years shall be a citizen of India. I had asked the Honourable Commerce Minister (when Mr. C. H. Bhabha was in charge) a question, when sitting in the other Chamber, as to whether there was any register of foreigners coming to India. He said "No". I asked if there were any rules and regulations governing the entry into the country of people from foreign countries, and he said there were none. I have no doubt the situation continues very much the same today. Such is the administration that we have. Is it then wise that we should throw open our citizenship so indiscriminately? I do not side any ground whatsoever that we should do it, unless it is the specious, oft-repeated and nauseating principle of secularity of the State. I think that we are going too far in this business of secularity. Does it mean that we must wipe out our own people, that we must wipe them out in order to prove our secularity, that we must wipe out Hindus and Sikhs under the name of secularity, that we must undermine everything that is sacred and dear to the Indians' to prove that we are secular? I do not think that that is the meaning of secularity and if that is the meaning which people want to attach to that word "a secular state". I am sure the popularity of those who take that view will not last long in India. I submit therefore, that this discarded as we did

the previous article, because there is nothing that is right in it. If really we want a tentative definition we can have it from other people, who are probably wiser than us, and that should be quite enough for us. That is one of the definitions that I have proposed in, my amendment No. 164, viz., "Every person residing in India-

(a) who is born of Indian parents; or

(b) who is naturalized under the law of naturalization." (Constituent Assembly Debate, 1949)

On the face of it, Deshmukh's argument seems rather common sense and even eloquent. Much of our common political discourse around the concepts of citizenship and migration is based on this sort of argument. However, this argument has one tragic flaw, something inherent in all discourses of 'Nationality' yet completely ignored. Deshmukh himself may have figured out the flaw when he was questioned by Shibban Lal Saksena. The exchange is so instructive that it is worth quoting in full:

Prof. Shibban Lal Saksena (United Provinces: General):

You say, 'being born of Indian parents. How do you define 'Indian parents'?

Dr. P.S. Deshmukh:

I think it should refer to all those persons who are resident in India. It would be quite easy to define it. If the Professor thinks a definition is necessary, it would be quite easy to frame one.

Prof. Shibban Lal Saksena:

Then give a definition?

Dr. P.S. Deshmukh:

Yes.

I thought that an Indian is a very easily recognizable person. When combined with domicile, it is easier to define it. But if the Professor thinks that an Indian cannot be recognized and that it is necessary to lay down who is an Indian, what is his colour and complexion and so on, I would leave it to him to suggest a suitable definition. I think the existing definition is capable of being understood without any difficulty. I do not think that a definition is necessary for every expression used. If you examine the Constitutions of other countries, the Constitution of Poland for instance, you will find that all that they provided is that any person who is born of Polish parents is a citizen of Poland. They know who is a Pole, just as we know who is an Indian. I do not think therefore that any definition is necessary in this connection. If we want a tentative definition, an article which will serve as a transitory provision, my article should be quite enough." (Constituent Assembly Debate, 1949).

Notice how Deshmukh is unable to define an Indian despite having claimed that it is very 'easy' to recognize such a person. His whole argument depends upon the existence of a definition of Indian not based on residence, and this is precisely what he is unable to provide. The cultural and ethnic diversity of India prohibits him from making physical claims of Indian-ness (such as brown skin colour etc.), nor can he resort to a religious basis since Indian religions are wildly divergent from each other. The only basis he can and does resort to is the claim of 'Indian ancestry'. Who are these ancestors, we may ask? Since he cannot use a physical nor religious basis to identify the 'ancestors', he necessarily has to pick a residential basis. In other words, the so-called 'ancestors' are simply the people who lived and died in India.

This is the central contradiction of Deshmukh and thinkers of his ilk, who, on the one hand, claim that a domicile basis for citizenship makes citizenship 'cheap' and should be replaced with an ancestral basis of citizenship, which, unfortunately for them, is based on the domicile of the ancestors. Why is yesterday's domicile better than today's? I doubt that even they could answer that properly.

We earlier used the case of the French Revolution to illustrate that the upcoming 'bourgeois society' and the formation of the nation-state was responsible for the introduction of the 'French citizen' and the necessary foreigner, who was everything that the French citizen was not. Again we see the same case in India in 1949, a newly formed sovereign nation-state. This time the 'Foreigner' was Pakistani or Bangladeshi. The 'Foreigner' was Muslim and 'we' were Hindu, the 'Foreigner' were violent and 'we' were peaceful; again, the 'Foreigner' was everything 'we' were not. With this framework in mind, is it surprising that the Supreme Court considers the presence of illegal migrants from Bangladesh an act of "external aggression" (*Sonowal vs Union Of India*, 2005).

The whole point of this seemingly irrelevant historical exercise was to argue that the concept of 'citizenship' is by nature exclusive and culturally contingent. That is, it has depended on contingent circumstances of the past and is not in any way 'essential' to human society. If we accept this, then we have to conclude that a State has no moral reason whatsoever to discriminate against non-citizens, especially if they happen to be poor and homeless, as many of them actually are. Accepting this, we must be ready to rethink migration and the way we think and deal with it. Keeping this in mind, let us try and understand the controversial Citizenship Amendment Act of 2019.

3. PRESENT DAY DEBATES AND STRATEGIES

3.1 Citizenship Amendment Act 2019

In 2019, the Indian Parliament passed the amendment of the Citizenship Act of 1955. The new amendment, known as the Citizenship Amendment Act of 2019, allows non-muslim religiously persecuted minorities from Muslim majority countries such as Pakistan, Bangladesh and Afghanistan, to gain fast-track Indian Citizenship (TOI, 2020). The Act seems rather trivial, but the reaction to it, especially from the Muslim community, was anything but trivial. Scores of protests erupted across the country, mobilizing thousands of people to stand up in protest against the Act.

Why were these people so agitated against the Act? Were they against helping religiously persecuted minorities? Not at all. In fact, a good portion of them did help accommodate refugees from Rohingya who fled from Myanmar due to religious persecution. Why then were they against the Act? One of the most common responses to this question is that the Act is against the spirit of the Constitution, which resolutely prohibits discrimination on the basis of religion. The Act allows non-Muslims to get fast-track citizenship, but not to Muslims, and hence it was discriminatory.

Not only journalists but some respected legal scholars have also taken up this line of argument. For example, the prominent lawyer Ajit Joy wrote, "The CAA and the NRC have challenged the fundamental principles of equality and secularism of the Indian Constitution." (Joy, 2021). Another prominent lawyer, Shafeeq Mahajir, wrote, "Classification on the basis of religious identity violates Articles 14 and 21 of the Constitution, and offends the fundamental principle of 'secularism', which is enshrined as the basic structure of the Constitution." (Mahajir, 2021)

Unfortunately, this argument is flawed, as it does not make the basic distinction between 'positive and 'negative' discrimination. Positive discrimination refers to discrimination practised by the law in favour

of minority groups to reduce inequality and ensure that they are protected. The reservation of quotas based on caste is an example of positive discrimination. Negative discrimination, on the other hand, is discrimination practised unfavourably against a person or community. Refusing to hire lower caste people is an example of negative discrimination.

With the distinction in mind, we can see that the law resolutely prohibits negative discrimination. This fact knocks down the argument that the "CAA is against the principles of the Constitution". CAA is based on positive discrimination, and hence if we consider it against the principle of equality enshrined in the Constitution, we must also consider reservations and mandatory quotas as being violations of the Constitution, as they too are 'discriminatory'.

Another rather influential argument heard was that the CAA on its own is no problem, yet when combined with the implementation of the National Population Register (NPR) – which is a list of all people residing in India, including non-citizens- the combo becomes deadly. The NPR will snatch citizenships from all those who do not have the required paperwork, declaring them non-citizens. These non-citizens, if they are non-Muslim, can apply for a fast-track citizenship via the CAA and regain their citizenships while the poor Muslims will be left without a country, probably in mass migration camps.

This argument has gained a certain amount of plausibility ever since Amit Shah, the president of the BJP, claimed in a West Bengal rally "infiltrators are termites and we will weed them out when we come back to power". He further added, "The BJP would introduce NRC across the country and grant citizenship to each and every Hindu refugee in the country." (Ahmed, 2021)

How much weight you give to Amit Shah's words is up to you. Regardless, there are some very problematic statistical issues present in preparing a list of all people currently residing in India. These issues have already been highlighted by Amitabh Kundu and P.C Mohanan, I will be reiterating their arguments here (Kundu and Mohanan, 2021). Kundu and Mohanan write, "The rule specifies that information for the NPR will include the name of the person, her relationship to head of household, names of father, mother and spouse (if married), sex, date of birth, marital status, place of birth, nationality (as declared), present address of usual residence, duration of stay at present address, permanent residential address, occupation/activity and educational qualification. Data for this humongous database is to be collected for every resident from each household in the country." That is a lot of information to be collected from each and every household! That is not all, as Kundu and Mohanan point out "a lot of data in the NPR, like educational status, marital status, occupation etc. are also not constant for a person and given the time lag in the finalization of Citizenship Register, these could get outdated." (Kundu and Mohanan, 2021)

The only way that the government could actually carry out a proper state-wise NPR then is to do it over a very short period. Otherwise, the information can get seriously outdated and cause a bevy of legal problems. Not to mention that this has to be done for all of India simultaneously, rather than in a state-wise order as to avoid double counting. Both of these issues make implementing the NPR a Herculean task in terms of effort and money, and which in turn gives no benefit to anyone at all. Even as a vote-banking strategy, it is a joke considering the fact that voters won't necessarily appreciate anyone taking away their citizenship, even if they return it fast-track five years later. Also, the absence of citizenship will also strip away their voting powers, leaving them worthless even for vote-banking.

Given all these issues, it is unlikely that even the BJP will seriously consider implementing a nationwide NPR. Even the Prime Minister backpedalled on NPR a week later after Shah's announcement. Again,

what about Shah's claim? To that, we can only say that if we rightly balked when the Prime Minister promised every person in India a hefty sum of five lakhs, why shouldn't we balk now? Summing up, if the argument is correct, then CAA is not an issue, and NPR is so big of an issue that it is unlikely to ever be taken seriously, making it, for our purposes, a non-issue. As to why this whole thing was concocted is an interesting question, requiring more time and space than this, and so best left to better scholarship. I can and will attempt to sketch a plausible answer, one originally suggested by N.C Saxena.

3.2 The Political Strategy of The BJP; Incense and win!

N.C Saxena provides an interesting anecdote about how RSS leaders seek votes in rural villages. He writes, "One RSS leader once told me that when they go to the villages to seek votes, they always carry a video with them. I asked, 'Mohan Bhagawat's?' He said, 'No, Owaisi's, in which he says he will never chant Bharat Mata ki Jai even if a knife is put at his throat.' He added, 'Hindus then forget their economic woes and rush to the booth to vote for us'." (Saxena, 2021)

Notice how the RSS strategy involves invoking hatred for an 'other', rather than providing any sort of promises for a better future. This has precisely been the political strategy of the BJP; take some non-issue, lay it out on a religious line, light the match which starts a communal conflict and Voila! Here is your ready-made vote bank. N.C Saxena gives other examples of this in play. The simple case of Aligarh Muslim University being ruled a minority institution was used as fuel for mobilizing votes for the BJP. The banning of the novel "Satanic Verses" by Salman Rushdie was used by the BJP to mobilize Hindu votes to increase its share in Lok Sabha from just 2 seats in 1984 to 120 in 1991. Many such examples can be given, is this the same case for CAA? Let us illustrate.

Hilal Ahmed observed that the CAA 2019 is unique as it uses particularly religious language. He writes, "The CAA 2019 does not use the term "minority". Instead, it identifies six-non-Muslim communities. The naming of communities on a religious basis actually goes against the established Constitution principles. The Constitution introduces terms such as minority, Schedule Caste (S.C.) and Scheduled Tribe (S.T.) as secular administrative categories." (Ahmed, 2021) Notice how a persecuted minority of a Muslim country is very likely to be non-Muslim, and so functionally the same thing as Hindu, Christian, Buddhist etc. He further points out that this was not a simple mistake as "The MHA and the Legislative Department forcefully argued that the CAA was based on the gazette notification of 2015, hence there was no need to use the term religious persecution in the text of CAA." The calls for changing the categories from religious to administrative ones was ignored by the BJP.

Why did they do this? Especially considering the fact that, changing the categories wouldn't affect the law at all. Moreover, it would have even helped as it would've been passed smoothly without any noise. They did this because it would trigger Muslims, which would trigger Hindus, leading to them getting their vote bank served on a platter. Think about it, if the Act simply said that "Some minorities may get fast-track citizenships after being investigated by the Foreign Tribunal", who would start massive protests against it? But, on the other hand, if it was worded in such a way as to offend Muslims by consciously excluding them, then why wouldn't they start protesting? After they start protesting, what do you tell the Hindus? You tell them, "Look. These Muslims are protesting against an Act that allows persecuted Hindus to seek refuge in India. Clearly, they want to rid India of its native Hindu population." And Voila! Here is your Hindu vote bank, served on a silver platter.

Returning to citizenship and Deshmukh, one should be wonder if there is anything wrong with making citizenship 'cheap'? Do other countries have it 'expensive'? Here we analyze a sample of counties in terms of their leniency in granting citizenships.

3.3 How the Rest of the World Deals with Citizenship

3.3.1 Brazil

Brazil has been a country that has immigration on a huge scale. As of now, Brazil has about 1,504,736 migrants from 19 different countries around the world (NSRFRB, 2020). Migrants come to Brazil from as varied countries as Japan and the United Kingdom. Despite the already huge amount of refugees present there, the Brazilian Laws governing citizenship are relatively lenient with respect to granting citizenship to foreigners. The Article 112 of the Brazilian Constitution, with reference to the naturalization of foreign nationals, says:

"Brazilians are:

I. by birth:

- a. those born in the Federative Republic of Brazil, even though of foreign parents, provided that they are not in the service of their country;
- b. those born abroad of a Brazilian father or mother, so long as either is in the service of the Federative Republic of Brazil;
- c. those born abroad of a Brazilian father or mother, so long as they are registered at a proper Brazilian governmental office, or come to reside in the Federative Republic of Brazil and opt for Brazilian nationality at any time after reaching the age of majority;

II. by naturalization:

- a. those who, as set forth by law, acquire Brazilian nationality; for persons whose country of origin is Portuguese-speaking, only one uninterrupted year of residence and good moral character are required;
- b. foreigners of any nationality, resident in the Federative Republic of Brazil for more than fifteen uninterrupted years and without any criminal conviction, provided they request Brazilian nationality."

3.3.2 The United States

The United States of America has the largest number of international migrants in terms of absolute numbers of any country. As of 2019, the country has about 48,000,000 international refugees from all over the world (UNDESA, 2019). The largest number of immigrants usually are from Mexico. A large percentage of immigration also occurs illegally in the United States, which too, comes mostly from Mexico. Again, despite the huge amount of immigrants already present in the U.S., its laws granting citizenship are very lenient. To apply for naturalization to become a U.S. citizen, you must:

- a. Be at least 18 years of age at the time you file the application;
- b. Have been a lawful permanent resident for the past three or five years;
- c. Have continuous residence and physical presence in the United States;
- d. Be able to read, write, and speak basic English;
- e. Demonstrate good moral character;
- f. Demonstrate a knowledge and understanding of U.S. history and government;
- g. Demonstrate a loyalty to the principles of the U.S. Constitution; and
- h. Be willing to take the Oath of Allegiance. (USCIS, 2020)

3.3.3 Australia

Just after World War 2, Australia, facing a threat of Japanese invasion, launched a massive immigration program, which became commonly known as the "Ten Pound Poms". "Poms" refers to English people, while the "Ten Pounds" were the travelling fees to Australia. The only conditions required for the immigrants for gaining an Australian citizenship were to be of good health and under 45 years of age. This generous policy resulted in one million British workers migrating to Australia (Hammerton and Thomson, 2005).

Although the country later modified its liberal immigration program, it still is one of the reasons why Australia has a great 30% of its population to be of migrants (Australian Bureau of Statistics, 2020). The current citizenship program is still very liberal (compared to other standards) in its granting of citizenship. The eligibility criteria for citizenship are:

- a. Be a permanent resident or eligible New Zealand citizen when you apply.
- b. Be in Australia when your application is decided.
- c. Have spent time in Australia and know about the country.
- d. Intend to live in Australia or maintain a lasting link with Australia while overseas (Australian Ministry of Home Affairs, 2020)

3.3.4 Malaysia

In the context of Asian countries, Malaysia is known for its rather liberal and broad-minded approach towards multiculturalism and diversity. As of 2019, Malaysia has around 3 million migrants from over 18 countries (Statista, 2019). A large part of immigrants is from China and India.

Regarding granting citizenship, in Article 16 of the Malaysian Constitution, the criteria for gaining Malaysian citizenship are:

"the Federal Government may, in such special circumstances as it thinks fit, upon application made by any person of or over the age of twenty-one years who is not a citizen, grant a certificate of naturalization to that person if satisfied -

- a. that he has resided in the Federation during the seven years immediately preceding the date of the application, for periods amounting in the aggregate to not less than five years;
- b. that he intends to do so permanently;
- c. that he is of good character; and
- d. that he has an elementary knowledge of the Malay language."

3.3.5 Germany

Germany has one of the largest shares of the immigrant population in the world. 19% of the country's population is composed of immigrants. As of 2020, Germany is home to around 15 million international immigration (Migration Policy Institute, 2020). Despite this, the citizenship policy of Germany is again, rather lenient. In order for a person to gain a German citizenship, one must:

"A foreigner who has been legally ordinarily resident in Germany for eight years and possesses legal capacity as defined in Section 37 or has a legal representative must be naturalized upon application if his or her identity and citizenship have been established and he or she

- a. confirms his or her commitment to the free democratic constitutional system enshrined in the Basic Law of the Federal Republic of Germany and declares that he or she does not pursue or support and has never pursued or supported any activities
 - i. aimed at subverting the free democratic constitutional system, the existence or security of the Federation or a Land or
 - ii. aimed at illegally impeding the constitutional bodies of the Federation or a Land or the members of said bodies in discharging their duties or
 - iii. jeopardizing foreign interests of the Federal Republic of Germany through the use of violence or preparatory actions for the use of violence or credibly asserts that he or she has distanced him- or herself from the former pursuit or support of such activities,
- b. has been granted a permanent right of residence or as a national of Switzerland or as a family member of a national of Switzerland possesses a residence permit.
- c. is able to support him- or herself and his or her dependants without recourse to benefits, or if recourse to such benefits is due to conditions beyond his or her control,
- d. gives up or loses his or her previous citizenship,
- e. has not been sentenced for an unlawful act and is not subject to any court order imposing a measure of reform and prevention due to a lack of criminal capacity,
- f. has sufficient command of the German language,
- g. possesses knowledge of the legal system, society and living conditions in the Federal Republic of Germany, and it is guaranteed that he or she accepts German social norms, in particular the prohibition on polygamous marriages”

3.3.6 The United Kingdom

To acquire a British Citizenship one must satisfy the following conditions:

- a. Five years' legal residence in the UK
- b. Indefinite leave to remain or "equivalent" for this purpose (see above), must have held it for 12 months
- c. the applicant must intend to continue to live in the British Islands or work overseas for the British government or a British corporation or association
- d. the same "good character" standards apply as for those married to British citizens
- e. the same language and knowledge of life in the UK standards apply as for those married to British citizens (Gov.uk, 2021)

3.3.7. France

To acquire a French Citizenship, one must satisfy the following conditions as laid down by the Article 21-17 by the French Civil Constitution.

- a. One must be above 18 years of age
- b. One must have resided in France for more than 5 years
- c. In addition, it is required that the applicant has his/her primary source of income in France during the five-year period.

- d. Those applying who are not European Union, European Economic Area or Swiss nationals are required to be in possession of a residence permit.

As we can see, almost all of the seven countries listed here, have much more leniency in granting citizenships than India, which requires a mandatory stay of twelve years for naturalization. Deshmukh may have gotten his wish of preventing the Indian citizenship becoming cheap. There is a subtle irony here; despite the Indian citizenship being expensive, India as a whole became cheap. Of all of the countries listed here, India ranks the lowest in development.

4. HOW FOREIGN MIGRANTS HELP COUNTRIES

Discussions on the area of citizenship often run into the issue of migrants. This was as true at the time of Deshmukh as it is of now. There are various myths surrounding migrants, most notably, the one that they 'steal' the native population's jobs. Various empirical and theoretical rebuttals have been advanced and so that does not concern us here. Interested readers can see Peri (2014).

The fact about migrants is that they contribute a good deal of income to their parent countries. A good portion of migrants usually migrate to get better job prospects in other countries. Most of them do not migrate with their families and hence plan on earning enough money in other countries as to support their families at home.

For the past twenty years, remittances sent by migrants to their home countries have increased at a relatively steady pace. Here we present data from countries around the world to show the increase in migrant remittances from 2000 to 2020. The remittances are measured in US dollars (nominal).

4.1 Brazil

Source: World Bank staff calculation based on data from IMF Balance of Payments Statistics database and data releases from central banks, national statistical agencies, and World Bank country desks. See *Migration and Development Brief 28, Appendix A* for details.

4.2 China

Source: World Bank staff calculation based on data from IMF Balance of Payments Statistics database and data releases from central banks, national statistical agencies, and World Bank country desks. See Migration and Development Brief 28, Appendix A for details.

4.3 Denmark

Source: World Bank staff calculation based on data from IMF Balance of Payments Statistics database and data releases from central banks, national statistical agencies, and World Bank country desks. See Migration and Development Brief 28, Appendix A for details.

4.4 India

Source: World Bank staff calculation based on data from IMF Balance of Payments Statistics database and data releases from central banks, national statistical agencies, and World Bank country desks. See Migration and Development Brief 28, Appendix A for details.

4.5 Indonesia

Source: World Bank staff calculation based on data from IMF Balance of Payments Statistics database and data releases from central banks, national statistical agencies, and World Bank country desks. See Migration and Development Brief 28, Appendix A for details.

4.6 Russia

Source: World Bank staff calculation based on data from IMF Balance of Payments Statistics database and data releases from central banks, national statistical agencies, and World Bank country desks. See Migration and Development Brief 28, Appendix A for details.

4.7 Turkey

Source: World Bank staff calculation based on data from IMF Balance of Payments Statistics database and data releases from central banks, national statistical agencies, and World Bank country desks. See Migration and Development Brief 28, Appendix A for details.

4.8 United Kingdom

Source: World Bank staff calculation based on data from IMF Balance of Payments Statistics database and data releases from central banks, national statistical agencies, and World Bank country desks. See Migration and Development Brief 28, Appendix A for details.

4.9 United States

Source: World Bank staff calculation based on data from IMF Balance of Payments Statistics database and data releases from central banks, national statistical agencies, and World Bank country desks. See Migration and Development Brief 28, Appendix A for details.

As we can see, 7 out of the 9 countries listed here has seen a steady increase in remittances by migrants. These remittances are often very beneficial to the native country and do help in its development.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper, tries to establish these points; (a) The concept of 'citizenship' is nothing 'natural' and was and is evolving, (b) The main function of a modern 'citizen' is to exclude foreigners. Combining (a) and (b) in lieu of CAA 2019, the paper tries to show that (c) CAA 2019 is simply a trivial issue, flamed with reactionary rhetoric in order to incense Muslims. Furthermore, looking at it from a global perspective, it seems that many developed countries have rather lenient forms of granting citizenships to their immigrant populations, something which is something strange in the current Indian context. The popular myth about migrants causing harm has been put to rest in many places, here we show that migrants are a tremendous boon for the mother country as they send large amounts of remittances to it.

If these three are established, where do we go from here? It will be fruitful, that we do away with the narrow concept of 'citizen', to a broader concept of 'cosmopolitan', which means, a member of the 'cosmos'. It is possible, that this broader vision of humanity is necessary if we wish to discard our past history of incessant wars and jingoism. Concerns for the environment also fit in well with the broader notion of cosmopolitanism rather than citizenship. The Greek economist Yanis Varoufakis pointed out "Looking at it from space, all borders seem an absurdity." (Varoufakis, 2015).

The questions of economic inequality also need to be addressed appropriately. How can a beggar and a billionaire be treated equally? Massive amounts of inequalities regularly corrode normal citizenships. One can imagine what it'll do to a broader notion of cosmopolitanism.

These ideas are nothing new. These were present thousands of years ago. It is a shame that they haven't been implemented. The ancient philosopher Epictetus, writing in 100 AD, said:

If the things are true which are said by the philosophers about the kinship between God and man, what else remains for men to do than what Socrates did? Never in reply to the question, to what country you belong, say that you are an Athenian or a Corinthian, but that you are a citizen of the world. For why do you say that you are an Athenian, and why do you not say that you belong to the small nook only into which your poor body was cast at birth? Is it not plain that you call yourself an Athenian or Corinthian from the place which has a greater authority and comprises not only that small nook itself and all your family, but even the whole country from which the stock of your progenitors is derived down to you? He then who has observed with intelligence the administration of the world, and has learned that the greatest and supreme and the most comprehensive community is that which is composed of men and God, and that from God have descended the seeds not only to my father and grandfather, but to all beings which are generated on the Earth and are produced, and particularly to rational beings—for these only are by their nature formed to have communion with God, being by means of reason conjoined with him—why should not such a man call himself a citizen of the world, why not a son of God, and why should he be afraid of anything which happens among men? Is kinship with Caesar (the emperor) or with any other of the powerful in Rome sufficient to enable us to live in safety, and above (contempt and without any fear at all? and to have God for your maker, and father and guardian, shall not this release us from sorrows and fears?" (Long, 1904).

These words of Epictetus are some rather powerful words, yet are simply words nonetheless. To transform them into action is what is required. Whether or not we are able to do this may as well determine our collective selves plunge into disaster, or we rise up to new heights. The questions are not only theoretical but substantive and practical, and to answer them is to answer them in theory as well as in practice.

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